

Recommended citation: Uthrapathi Shakila, N., Nizamis, K., Poortman, C., & van der Veen, J. (2021). Interdisciplinary Challenge-based learning: Science to Society. In Heiß, H.-U., Järvinen, H.-M., Mayer, A., & Schulz, A. (Eds.), *Blended Learning in Engineering Education: challengingm enlightening and lasting? SEFI 49th Annual Conference* (pp. 1511-1519). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Berlin, Germany. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14651558.

INTERDISCIPLINARY CHALLENGE-BASED LEARNING: SCIENCE TO SOCIETY

N. Uthrapathi Shakila¹

University of Twente, ELAN
Enschede, The Netherlands

K. Nizamis

University of Twente, ET
Enschede, The Netherlands

C. L. Poortman

University of Twente, ELAN
Enschede, The Netherlands

J.T. van der Veen

Eindhoven University of Technology, ESoE
Eindhoven, The Netherlands

Conference Key Areas: *Teaching methodology, competence development*

Keywords: *Interdisciplinarity, challenge-based learning, societal problems*

ABSTRACT

There is a growing recognition that the world's emerging complex problems require perspectives from multiple disciplines to be properly addressed. For higher education, it is imperative to develop well-rounded graduates with both a depth and breadth of knowledge and skills to integrate perspectives across disciplines. A mixed-methods study was conducted to describe the implementation of an interdisciplinary module with students from nine bachelor programs across science, engineering and social sciences who worked on a challenge-based learning assignment. This module involved external partners setting the 'challenges', and the student groups worked on devising an interdisciplinary solution. For students, multiple available options for support such as tutors, lecturers and challenge partners were found to be an enabling factor. At the same time, the minimally structured learning activities, and ambiguity of expectations were the limiting factors. At the staff level, the lack of cohesion within the teaching team and minimal support for guiding student groups were limiting factors. In terms of collaboration in the groups, students recognized the role of the other disciplines, improved their communication, and integrated disciplinary knowledge at varying levels.

¹ *Corresponding Author*
N. Uthrapathi Shakila
niveditha.u.s@gmail.com

They faced difficulties such as an unequal distribution of workload and disciplinary differences, causing tension. Lastly, the key competencies developed in the module were perspective-taking, communication, collaboration, reflection, and confidence in existing skills and knowledge. Main recommendations for improving the module are scaffolding support for students, developing the interdisciplinary teaching team, and guiding the challenge definition process.

1 INTRODUCTION

Interdisciplinary (ID) education aims to help students in learning how to address complex real-world problems [1][2]. Interdisciplinarity stands out in its integration of multiple disciplines triggered by a shared problem that spans across disciplines, thereby necessitating collaboration [3][4]. ID education can be facilitated through active learning pedagogies coupled with student collaboration, and an iterative process designed with milestones and scaffolds [5]. Building further on the concept of ID education, challenge-based learning (CBL) is specialized for diverse teams working on solving real-life problems in a systematic method [6]. In CBL, instead of being provided with a problem, students must define a challenge from general authentic problems shared by industry partners, and are encouraged to work with peers, teachers, and external partners to devise a solution [7].

This research is a descriptive case study conducted on an undergraduate interdisciplinary minor, Science2Society 'From Idea to Prototype' at the University of Twente. The module adopted the CBL approach to facilitate ID education for students from nine different disciplines across applied and social sciences. Since the context includes very distant disciplines, the results can encourage and guide broader ID education with CBL. This study aims to examine the following research focus areas about the implementation of ID challenge-based education in this module: 1) perceived value of this module, 2) support for staff and students, 3) interdisciplinary group collaboration, and 4) competency outcomes.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Module

The module aimed to engage students from multiple disciplines to collaborate and address real-world challenges in diverse fields of Energy, Health, Learning, and Robotics that require an interdisciplinary approach through the integration of knowledge from different domains. It is a 15ECTS module organized across 10 weeks for 3rd year Bachelor students to develop scientifically and practically grounded prototype(s) addressing the challenge. The students worked in heterogeneous groups on a challenge for an external partner (e.g. Energy Transition towards Gasless Domestic Heating & Cooking for City of Enschede). Students were introduced to various scientific disciplines to develop a shared background knowledge to address the given challenge. The content was focused on Design, research and other skills were supported through specific workshops open to all students of the course.

2.2 Case study design

Participants: Students from nine study programs and staff involved in the implementation of the module across different roles were the participants (Table 1). Also, challenge providers (3) representing the partner organizations were interviewed.

Table 1. Participants

Students (48)	Staff (17)
1. Psychology (18)	1. Guest lecturers responsible for facilitating the workshops/lectures.
2. Mechanical Engineering (11)	2. Module coordinators responsible for organization and coordination.
3. Industrial Design Engineering (8)	3. Process tutors responsible for guiding the student groups.
4. Technical Medicine (2)	4. Challenge facilitators responsible for liaising between the challenge providers and the groups.
5. Chemical Science and Engineering (2)	5. Educational specialists who guided the design of this module
6. International Business Administration (1)	
7. Electrical Engineering (1)	
8. Computer Science (1)	
9. University College ATLAS (1)	

Instruments: An online survey (89% response rate) was used to collect self-report data from the students about their experience in the module. In total, 15 questions were presented with ten closed-ended five point Likert scale questions and five open-ended questions to gather qualitative comments. The closed questions were adapted from Lattuca's measures of ID competence [8], and previous ID education studies [9][10][11][12]. Semi-structured focus group interviews were conducted with 7 students to zoom in on their experience. Individual semi-structured interviews were used to understand the perspectives of 17 academic staff involved in the module. The interview scheme consisted of 10 questions focused on their experience in the module, and opinions about student collaboration and competency outcomes. Furthermore, observations and document analyses were performed to understand the support structures, intended competency outcomes and collaboration experience.

Data analysis: The quantitative data from the survey were analysed in IBM SPSS 24. Qualitative data from the other sources were thematically analyzed using Atlas.ti 9 following phases of thematic analysis [13]. Triangulation was key to interpreting the data to identify convergence, complementarity, and dissonance among the findings for relevant research questions [14].

3 RESULTS

Perceived Value: Overall, staff members valued ID education positively (See Table 2). The exposure to authentic problems, and working with students from other disciplines were shared as strengths of this module, as illustrated in this interview fragment:

“I think having the challenge provider was very nice because they (students) got to interact with the real-life company or a case....The interdisciplinary team is again a huge strength. So being able to work with people from different fields and get to know how to speak to people from different fields.”

Students' responses also point to a better understanding of the challenge due to ID, relevance for the future, and higher motivation due to authentic challenges. The following comment by a student exemplifies this aspect well:

“(In previous projects) I often had the feeling that we are working several weeks on one problem and then we come up with a solution. But nobody cares about the solution because it's just on your paper and you get a grade and that's it. And with the (challenge provider), we can actually do something that they can use. So, you are more motivated to work because, you know, they really want to use it.”

Table 2. Highlights reported by staff (n=22)

Highlights	Occurrence
Enhanced competencies	11
Relevancy for future profession	10
Broadened perspectives	9
New insights from other fields	4

Support: Staff were satisfied with the organization and communication within the module and expressed their interest to be more involved. Lecturers proposed improved alignment of the lectures and other learning activities with the intended outcomes. Challenge facilitators shared their interest to join the lectures and workshops to be aware of the educational aspects. Process tutors appreciated the CBL workshop they received and shared that they would like more clarity on their responsibilities for guiding the student groups. Module coordinators suggested that professional support for guiding ID education would be beneficial for all.

Students appreciated the availability of multiple options for support in this module, and they were largely positive towards the support they received. Planned support was in the form of *content* support from lecturers and challenge providers, *supervisory* support from process tutors and challenge facilitators, and *infrastructural* support through the learning management system of the module and a working space for weekly meetings. All participants specifically pointed out the involvement of the challenge provider for contextual support as an enabling factor. Besides, the group members supported each other. On the other hand, one of the limiting factors was the lack of alignment between the learning objectives and learning activities in the module. Also, the staff pointed out

the lack of material and challenge-specific resources in the module as a potential limitation for students. Students, brought up limited interaction with other groups, struggles with group formation and finding the ideal composition, and suggested additional support for group work.

Collaboration: Collaboration was largely driven by dividing tasks within the ID group based on disciplinary expertise. It was also unanimously noted that the contribution to the project varied among the disciplines involved in a group (See Table 3). Next, the aspect of differing perspectives across the disciplines and some prejudice about students of other disciplines was noted. Students highlighted the learning resulting from collaboration, communication struggles among different disciplines, and difficulties in making decisions as a team. Examples of comments about collaboration from students:

On different approaches: *“We all have different approaches .. the psychology students’ approach is more like scientific. So, you start with working on your theory and you start working on the analysis of the problem.... The engineering students’ approach is more practical, they wanted to start right at the beginning with the prototyping and everything.”*

On communication: *“Sometimes, if we have a certain idea, it’s hard for others to understand what you mean with it. So, the other Industrial Design students understand but like a Computer Science student doesn’t understand what exactly you mean. And it’s difficult to explain what you mean and then have some kind of discussion and then try to figure out.”*

Table 3. Student responses about the nature of collaboration in their group

Nature of collaboration	Percentage
We divided the tasks based on our expertise	87%
We formed sub-groups to tackle the challenge	77%
We worked on tasks individually and coordinated our work in the meetings	46%
We engaged in group work most of the time and shared our expertise	36%
Students of certain disciplines had more or less work in our project	28%
We all had an equal role in the project	26%

Competencies developed: The competencies developed through the module were determined based on the intended learning outcomes and what was anticipated by the lecturers, and what was perceived by the students and the staff who worked directly with the student groups. The overall key trends are collaboration, communication, confidence in self and their disciplinary knowledge, reflection, and perspective-taking. The following is a comment by a student about perspective taking:

“Not having ‘tunnel vision’ on the problem by only looking at it from your own discipline. I learned to look at it from multiple perspectives”

4 CONCLUSIONS & DISCUSSION

Value: Staff members and students predominantly shared a positive attitude towards this unique module [15][16]. Students are motivated by working on authentic challenges [6][17]. Moreover, the involvement of external challenge providers is vital as it deepens the rationale for ID education and allows for diversity in solutions [18][19].

Support: The workshop for the process tutors was regarded positively and is aligned to the theoretical recommendations for training supervisors [20]. Staff's prior experience in ID is an important factor as previous studies have shown that ID experience can increase investment and ability to guide students [21]. However, the lack of cohesion among the staff team can hinder ID collaboration as staff's role-modelling of valuing other disciplines and integrating disciplinary perspectives is essential [22]. Limited training for staff is concerning as previous studies have highlighted the need for training staff on supervising interdisciplinary teams and guiding students towards integration and open-ended problem solving [21].

The module demands the students to be self-directed in their learning with limited guidance. Although the intention is to develop students' professional competencies and self-regulation through this design, it is important to note that scaffolding is crucial in supporting the transition from learning with well-defined expectations to self-directed ID group work [5][22]. Previous studies in ID have reported students pointing out lack of support [19] and asking for more checkpoints for feedback [22]. However, a fine balance must be reached in terms of structure as too much structure can negatively impact ID collaboration. Therefore, instead of prescribing the approaches or outcomes, students may be supported by including activities that encourage ID teamwork and guide integrated problem-solving [15].

Collaboration: Students from many disciplines in ID education can work together and acquire new skills. Although there are differing levels of integration, evidently the students prefer to bring their own expertise leading to disciplinary division of tasks. Previous studies have been critical of this approach as it can prevent integration between disciplines [23]. Linked to this, there was unequal contribution as certain disciplines did not have as much to add from their disciplinary knowledge. Managing and distributing workloads among disciplines in groups are common problems in interdisciplinary contexts due to unequal disciplinary grounding and sequential order of involvements of the disciplines [24]. Also, communication problems occur due to the use of significantly different vocabulary among disciplines. This necessitates simplifying and articulating one's ideas [24][25]. Struggles with decision making can be attributed to inherent differences in theory, methodologies, and epistemologies across disciplines

and causes difficulties for students to navigate learning in ID groups [4]. This adds to the need for scaffolded support.

Competency outcomes: The competencies of communication, collaboration, reflection, perspective-taking, and confidence in prior knowledge, were improved based on student and staff perceptions. Students developing the competencies of drawing connections to prior knowledge and between disciplines is notable. The skill of seeing connections across disciplines is a key interdisciplinary skill and a starting point for curiosity, respect, and openness related to the appreciation of other disciplines [8][4]. Competency development in students can be attributed to both the interdisciplinary and challenge-based learning elements of the module which offer them the opportunity and demand to expand their repertoire of skills.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, recommendations to further strengthen this and other interdisciplinary modules are relevant. Firstly, scaffolding tools can help support and understand group processes [27], discourse frameworks [26], reflective dialogue for assessments [5], and process management methods such as Scrum [28]. Moreover, milestones with planned feedback moments aligned to all the learning objectives can help streamline the student team process. Secondly, developing the teacher team in how they can support the student groups to collaborate and effectively integrate their disciplines in response to the challenge. Thirdly, ensuring constructive alignment between all the learning objectives, activities and the assessment. Fourth, introducing peer assessment for the dual benefits of getting groups to leverage their peers for support and sharing innovative practices (e.g. group processes or involving stakeholders). Lastly, the recruitment of challenges can be improved to ensure that the external partners are aware of their expected involvement and needs of group composition. As the onus of defining the problem from the challenge description is on the students, they need support to ensure disciplinary perspectives are balanced.

REFERENCES

- [1] National Academy of Sciences, I. (2005). *Facilitating Interdisciplinary Research*. National Academies Press.
- [2] Khadri, H. O. (2014). A Strategy for Developing and Enhancing Interdisciplinary Research and Graduate Education at Ain Shams University (ASU), 10(28).
- [3] Mansilla, V. B., & Duraising, E. D. (2007). Targeted assessment of students' interdisciplinary work: An empirically grounded framework proposed. *Journal of Higher Education*, 78(2), 215-237.
- [4] Spelt, E. J., Luning, P. A., van Boekel, M. A., & Mulder, M. (2015). Constructively aligned teaching and learning in higher education in engineering: what do students perceive as contributing to the learning of interdisciplinary thinking? *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 40(5), 459-475.
- [5] Manathunga, C., Lant, P., & Mellick, G. (2007). Developing professional researchers: Research students' graduate attributes. *Studies in Continuing Education*, 29(1), 19-36.
- [6] Rådberg, K. K., Lundqvist, U., Malmqvist, J., & Svensson, O. H. (2020). From CDIO to challenge based learning experiences—expanding student learning as well as societal impact? *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 45(1), 22-37.
- [7] Gaskins, W. B., Johnson, J., Maltbie, C., & Kukreti, A. R. (2015, 2). Changing the Learning Environment in the College of Engineering and Applied Science Using Challenge Based Learning. *International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy (iJEP)*, 5(1), 33-41.
- [8] Lattuca, L. R., Knight, D., & Bergom, I. (2013, 1). Developing a measure of interdisciplinary competence. *International Journal of Engineering Education*, 29(3), 726-739.
- [9] Gero, A. (2017). Students' attitudes towards interdisciplinary education: a course on interdisciplinary aspects of science and engineering education. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 42(3), 260-270.
- [10] Johnson-Veldhuis, C. (2020). Challenges and value perceptions of an interdisciplinary module at the University of Twente: A descriptive study.
- [11] Richter, D. M., & Paretto, M. C. (2009). Identifying barriers to and outcomes of interdisciplinarity in the engineering classroom. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 34(1), 29-45.
- [12] Norris, J., Carpenter, J. G., Eaton, J., Guo, J.-W., Lassche, M., Pett, M. A., & Blumenthal, D. K. (2015, 10). The Development and Validation of the Interprofessional Attitudes Scale. *Academic Medicine*, 90(10), 1394-1400.
- [13] Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77-101.
- [14] Adams, J., Bateman, B., Becker, F., Cresswell, T., Flynn, D., McNaughton, R., Oluboyede, Y., Robalino, S., Ternent, L., Sood, B., Michie, S.,

- Shucksmith, J., Sniehotta, F., & Wigham, S. (2015). Chapter 6: Triangulation and integration of results. *Health Technology Assessment* 19(94), 1-176.
- [15] Borrego, M., Karlin, J., McNair, L. D., & Beddoes, K. (2013). Team Effectiveness Theory from Industrial and Organizational Psychology Applied to Engineering Student Project Teams: A Research Review. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 102(4), 472-512.
- [16] van den Beemt, A., MacLeod, M., der Veen, J. V., de Ven, A. V., van Baalen, S., Klaassen, R., & Boon, M. (2020). Interdisciplinary engineering education: A review of vision, teaching, and support. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 109(3), 508-555.
- [17] Brundiers, K., Wiek, A., & Redman, C. L. (2010). Real-world learning opportunities in sustainability: from classroom into the real world. *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*.
- [18] Hannon, J., Hocking, C., Legge, K., & Lugg, A. (2018). Sustaining interdisciplinary education: developing boundary crossing governance. *Higher Education Research and Development*, 37(7), 1424-1438.
- [19] MacLeod, M., & van der Veen, J. T. (2020). Scaffolding interdisciplinary project-based learning: a case study. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 45(3), 363-377.
- [20] Schaddelee, M., & McConnell, C. (2018). Analysing student perceptions to enhance engagement: An interdisciplinary, project-based learning programme. *Journal of International Education in Business*, 11(2), 161-177.
- [21] Lyall, C., Meagher, L., Bandola, J., & Kettle, A. (2015). Interdisciplinary provision in higher education. *Higher Education Academy*, 1-97.
- [22] Stentoft, D. (2017). From saying to doing interdisciplinary learning: Is problem-based learning the answer? *Active Learning in Higher Education*, 18(1), 51-61.
- [23] Jensen, A. A., Ravn, O., & Stentoft, D. (2019). Problem-Based Projects, Learning and Interdisciplinarity in Higher Education. 9-19.
- [24] Warr, M., & West, R. E. (2020). Bridging Academic Disciplines with Interdisciplinary Projectbased Learning. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Problem-Based Learning*, 14(1).
- [25] Repko, A. (2008). *Interdisciplinary Research: Process and Theory*. Thousand, Oaks, CA: SAGE.
- [26] Öberg, G. (2009). Facilitating Interdisciplinary Work: Using Quality Assessment to Create Common Ground. *Higher Education*, 57(4), 405-415.
- [27] Sortland, B. (Ed.). (2019). Experts in teamwork. *Handbook for village supervisor and learning assistants* (9th ed.). Trondheim, Norway: NTNU.
- [28] Magnell, M., & Högfeldt, A.K. (2016.). Guide to challenge driven education: *ECE Teaching and Learning in Higher Education* (1). 85.